

Update on the US Extremely Large Telescope Program

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The US Extremely Large Telescope Program (US-ELTP) is a partnership among the Giant Magellan Telescope (GMT) and Thirty Meter Telescope (TMT) observatory projects and AURA/NOIRLab. The goal of the US-ELTP is to complete the construction of the two observatories and ensure US community access to full-sky data from the next-generation state-of-the-art telescopes. The role of NSF's NOIRLab is to provide the end-to-end system for proposal submission and evaluation; generation of observing programs for adaptive, integrated scheduling; robust automated standard data

reduction pipelines; complete curation of all data; and support of a data science platform, based on the heritage of its efforts for the Gemini and Rubin Observatories and the Community Science and Data Center.

The plan is to provide high-quality, easy-to-use tools accessible by any community user and to support a means for fostering collaborations to lower the barrier to participation in cutting-edge science with these telescopes, enabling high-impact investigations and furthering community goals

US-ELTP exhibit at AAS Meeting #241 in Seattle, Washington, with staff from the three partners. *Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA*

for research inclusion. The three partners (GMT, TMT, and AURA/NOIRLab) communicate closely and often at management and technical levels to assure that the parallel developments are mutually supportive in realizing the US-ELTP's goals.

Considerable progress has been made over the last several months. The NSF Astronomy Division conducted preliminary design reviews for the two telescope projects in December and January. The projects used the opportunity to demonstrate their technical innovation and readiness, risk mitigations, and rigorous management and business practices. At NOIRLab, under the guidance of Steve Berukoff, the Program Manager, and Marie Lemoine-Busserolle, the Systems Scientist, the US-ELTP team has advanced the flow-down from scientific and operational needs to (over 700) system requirements, and work is underway on an integrated conceptual design. André-Nicolas Chené, the Community Engagement Scientist, worked with the telescope projects and NOIRLab's Communications, Education, and Engagement Service to create an eye-catching US-ELTP exhibit at the Seattle AAS meeting in January and the Albuquerque AAS meeting in June. He is also updating the US-ELTP website. Dara Norman and her postdoc, Tim Sacco, have produced an initial version of the [Toolkit of Collaborative Practice](#), which is an important step on the road to having a large community ready to benefit from ELT data as soon as the observatories begin their scientific operations. Eric Peng has now joined the team as Project Scientist, while Mark Dickinson is taking a well-earned sabbatical. We particularly welcome Lucas Macri, who is the new NOIRLab US-ELTP Director as of 01 May.

It has been a privilege for me to serve as Interim Program Director during these last months. By mutual agreement, I will be continuing to advise the program leadership. At the time of this writing, our astronomy colleagues at NSF are confronting the challenge of gaining approval and the financial resources necessary for the telescopes and the user support development to advance to construction. NOIRLab works with them closely in the spirit of the Cooperative Agreement to support their efforts to make the highest recommendation of the Decadal Survey for ground-based astronomy a reality.

New NOIRLab US ELT Program Director

Lucas Macri became the Program Director of the US Extremely Large Telescope Program (US-ELTP) on 01 May. The Program Director has overall leadership responsibility for the execution of the work and for meeting the science requirements within schedule and budget. Lucas is responsible for setting the strategic vision and priorities for the project. He acts as the main point of contact with NSF, AURA Corporate, and the NOIRLab Director's Office and represents the program in both internal and external committees and in public settings.

Lucas brings recent valuable experience as Professor of Physics and Astronomy and Associate Dean in the College of Science (later Arts & Sciences) of Texas A&M University, as Chair of the Executive Board of the LSST Corporation, and as a member of the Space Telescope Science Institute Council. He received a BS in Physics from MIT and a PhD in Astronomy from Harvard. He held Hubble and Goldberg Fellowships at NOAO, so his new appointment is a welcome return back to Tucson. The primary focus of his research has been in the extragalactic distance scale, using Cepheids and Miras to calibrate SNe Ia and measure the Hubble constant with increasing accuracy and precision.